

A PATH TO PERMANENCE

Navigating Archival Export from Salesforce for Grantmaking Organizations

REPORT FROM THE ROCKEFELLER ARCHIVE CENTER

JUNE 2026

Prepared By:

Hillel Arnold – Associate Director of Archives Chief Digital Strategy Officer, Rockefeller Archive Center

Hannah Sistrunk – User Experience and Accessibility Analyst, Rockefeller Archive Center

Advisory Committee Contributors:

Rashmi Batra – Director of the Office of COO and Application Engineering, Open Society Foundations

Juliana Chessin – Director, Grants Management, Commonwealth Fund

Hannah Kahn – Director, Grants Management, Hewlett Foundation

Julio Lopez – Manager of Technology, Gates Archive

Randy Manion – Deputy Director, Investment Management & CRM Applications, IT Operations, Gates Foundation

Mar Paricio Sunyer – Senior Business Analyst, Operations, The Rockefeller Foundation

Gaby Shorr – Grants Manager, Leon Levy Foundation

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	1
Purpose and Scope	1
Background and Methodology	2
Archival Export of Grant Information from Salesforce	2
Stakeholders and Motivations	4
Significant Variations in Salesforce Implementations	7
Existing Export Options.....	9
Gap Analysis of Existing Solutions Against Archival Export Requirements	13
Conclusion.....	16
Acknowledgements.....	17

Executive Summary

This report defines the use cases and requirements for archival export of grant information from the Salesforce platform and evaluates existing Salesforce and third-party export solutions against them. The analysis finds that given the complexity of the platform, variation of implementations, and organizational diversity, no one tool fully supports the regular export of structured grant data and associated documents in ways that also preserve context, enable the exclusion of sensitive information, and support sustainable implementation across organizations of different sizes and capacities. Additionally, no single path exists to manage archival information once it has been exported from Salesforce. To implement workable solutions, organizations must combine tools with a careful consideration of local requirements, existing infrastructure, and capacity for ongoing data governance and operational maintenance.

Purpose and Scope

Many grantmaking foundations rely on Salesforce and Salesforce-based products to manage grantmaking activities and their associated records. To preserve records of enduring value beyond the lifespan of these operational systems, these organizations must export information in ways that facilitate long-term preservation while supporting data governance requirements and working within operational constraints.

This report examines the current realities of archival export from Salesforce for grantmaking organizations. It identifies the core requirements, describes the landscape of existing export tools and contexts, provides an analyzes of the extent to which existing solutions meet the requirements, and offers a set of considerations and recommendations for organizations of all sizes and capacities to plan and implement solutions for archival export from Salesforce. Effective archival export depends on records management practices that identify information of enduring value, define retention and disposition requirements, and establish controls for sensitive information. Therefore, the export tools and workflows discussed in this report should be understood as one component in a broader framework of records management.

While this report offers a point-in-time review and analysis of the current Salesforce data export domain, Salesforce tooling and data structures continue to evolve rapidly, and products and associated workflows will inevitably shift over time. Acknowledging the reality of changing technologies, this analysis and its conclusions are rooted in the evergreen realities of the lack of investment and product development in the areas of data export from proprietary systems and in archives-specific use cases, how organizational size, structure, and resourcing impact solutions, and the basic requirements necessary to preserve and facilitate long-term access to grant records in archives.

Background and Methodology

Building from the recent [Fluxx Exporter project](#) to improve archival exports from the Fluxx grants management system that the Rockefeller Archive Center (RAC) completed jointly with Columbia University's Rare Book and Manuscript Library, the RAC undertook a related effort to support archival export from Salesforce. With the mission of collecting, managing, preserving, and providing broad and equitable access to the historical records of philanthropy and other efforts to work on behalf of the public good, the RAC maintains an interest in supporting the permanent retention of these records across the sector.

The RAC Digital Strategies team convened and worked closely with an advisory committee of grants management, technology, and business analysis leaders and practitioners across foundations with experience using Salesforce to manage grant data. This report is the culmination of a five-month research process informed by a series of advisory committee meetings and follow-up conversations with members designed to solicit and synthesize expert advice, feedback, and shared experiences; research and review Salesforce and third-party tool documentation; and develop requirements drawn from archives best practices and user researcher conducted with stakeholders as part of the Fluxx Exporter project. Based on the defined requirements, stakeholder group profiles, and details about existing implementation variations and solutions, the analysis identifies gaps between existing solutions and the needs of grantmaking organizations to provide actionable conclusions.

Archival Export of Grant Information from Salesforce

Defining Grant Information

Grant information documents the grantmaking process – the core business of many foundations – covering the entire grant lifecycle from application and review through disbursement of funds and final reporting.

While practices vary by foundation, grant information generally includes records submitted by grantees, additional information and process documentation created by foundation staff, and system-created data that documents automated actions (Figure 1). Some, but not all, of this information has enduring archival value. Archival grant information documents the grantmaking process without revealing financial, personally identifying, or organizationally sensitive data.

Figure 1. The major components of grant information and how they relate to each other. Note that components marked as containing “no archival elements” may contain elements available in other components that are considered archival. For example, an application that becomes a grant will have archival elements that become part of the grant record.

Defining Archival Export

Archival export is the creation of consistently structured and semantically meaningful packages of grant information that are intended to be ingested into archival systems for long-term preservation and access. These packages should contain only information with archival value, as defined above. Archival export generally occurs at the end of the grant lifecycle when the associated data is no longer being changed.¹ If there is a delay between export and ingest into archival systems, care must be taken to ensure the exported data is in sync with data stored in systems that are actively used.

Requirements for Archival Export

An implementation of archival export should support grantmaking organizations of all sizes, and include the following features:

¹ Some foundations may continue to use historical grant data for reporting or knowledge management purposes. While this may involve modifying these records in some ways (for example applying ontologies), there will still be a core set of data elements that remain unchanged. Organizations are encouraged to include these elements in archival export.

- Allow users to export both database-backed fields as well as attached documents to a simple directory structure.
- Export database-backed fields to one or more predictably named files, serialized as structured data.
- Export attached documents in the original file format in which they were uploaded.
- Allow users to select which database-backed fields and document types should be included in an export so that fields containing PII or other sensitive information can be excluded.
- Allow users to specify which grant records should be exported based on data in a database-backed field, such as grant status or grant close date, ensuring that only grant information that is no longer actively in use is exported.
- Export data on a pre-defined regular schedule or on demand.

Related Concepts

Although archival export bears some similarity to system backups and migrations, there are some important distinctions:

- Backups and migrations generally do not consider the sensitivity or relevance of information in grant records. An archival export only includes data that has archival value and is intended to be preserved and made available for access at some point.
- Backups and migrations also presume specific target systems. Packages created by archival export will likely be used in multiple systems to support preservation and access, so the exported package needs to be system-agnostic, standardized, and semantically meaningful.

Stakeholders and Motivations

Six primary stakeholder groups are involved in the archival export of grant data from Salesforce: grants managers, information and knowledge managers, foundation IT managers, learning and evaluation professionals, archivists, and archives users. These stakeholders represent the primary audiences for this report, as each plays a distinct role in defining requirements, implementing technical solutions, managing risk, stewarding archival records over time, or using information in archival records.

Specific titles and responsibilities vary across organizations; not every role exists in all contexts, and in some contexts one person could be covering multiple roles. Additionally, the groups identified here are scoped to include only people directly engaged with managing and using archival grant data; other stakeholders with approval and advisory roles, including executive and legal staff, are out of scope.

Grants Managers

Grants managers are responsible for ensuring their foundation's grantmaking operations support program strategy and goals.

Goals and Motivations

- Support understanding of and accountability for the grantmaking program by holistically documenting grantmaking activity.
- Identify and leverage grant information to assess, learn from, and generate new knowledge about past grantmaking activities.
- Improve organizational processes and alignment with funding goals.

Information and Knowledge Managers

Information and knowledge managers are responsible for managing a foundation's information assets.

Goals and Motivations

- Manage the disposition of information assets according to an established schedule that meets legal and regulatory requirements.
- Define and manage elements of the grant record that are of enduring value as well as elements that present organizational risk.
- Foster knowledge management to support organizational learning.
- Support operational needs of foundation, including grant-making activities, through efficient access to records for staff.
- Provide historical context of foundation activities for strategic decision makers.
- Provide backup of grant records as a category of vital records.
- As information systems and processes change, ensure training and understanding for other stakeholders.

Foundation IT Managers

Foundation IT managers are responsible for ensuring the stability, security, and performance of the foundation's technology environment, both on-premise and in the cloud.

Goals and Motivations

- Architect data strategy and implement and maintain technological tools that support the operational needs of the foundation.
- Lighten ongoing maintenance load by transitioning select applications to the cloud or SaaS models.
- Ensure application and network integrity and security.

- Integrate grants management systems with other enterprise systems and tools, including reporting and data analysis tools.
- Document and support the organizational understanding of available data and how data systems are integrated.
- Ensure the ongoing security of sensitive data.

Learning and Evaluation Professionals

Learning and evaluation professionals are responsible for assessing the outcomes and impact of a foundation's grantmaking and programs, and to enable organizational learning.

Goals and Motivations

- Access grant data to evaluate impact and effectiveness across programs and/or time periods.
- Analyze patterns and trends in past grantmaking activities to support organizational learning and inform future strategies.

Archivists

Archivists are responsible for acquiring, preserving, describing, and providing access to the records of multiple organizations, including foundations.

Goals and Motivations

- Ensure authenticity of digital records received from foundations.
- Provide meaningful public access to open records received from foundations.
- Ensure records of enduring value documenting the core activities of a foundation can be preserved over the long term.
- Preserve the full context of grantmaking activity, including both application data as well as supporting documents which describe the grantmaking process.

Archives Users

Users of archives seeking to find, identify, select, and use archival records for any purpose.

Goals and Motivations

- Be able to discover and access archival records via descriptive information about the records, record creators and other agents, activities, and the relationships between them.
- Be able to use, reuse, and share archival description data

Significant Variations in Salesforce Implementations

Because Salesforce is a platform rather than a product, implementations differ significantly, including the data models and APIs relevant to archival export. The following categories outline the main variations in Salesforce implementations that impact archival export currently in use in the philanthropic sector.

Versions

Salesforce Lightning is the current version of the platform, which includes component-based design, enhanced customization options, additional reporting tools (Lightning Report Builder), and AI integration (Einstein AI). Although Salesforce Classic was used previously, organizations in the sector have now migrated to Salesforce Lightning. Data and metadata are largely independent of whether an organization is using Classic or Lightning – both interfaces access the same underlying data model and APIs.

API Access

Salesforce bundles features and services into eight different editions. Out of these, API access is only enabled by default in Enterprise, Performance, Unlimited, and Developer Editions. It can be added to Professional Edition instances as an add-on.

To make an API call, a user must have the API Enabled permission turned on in their user profile. The user's profile and assigned permission sets determine which objects and fields within those objects the API connection can read, create, edit, or delete. In supported editions, it is also possible to grant system-to-system users API-only access via the Salesforce Integration user license.

Salesforce limits the number of API calls per organization on a 24-hour rolling basis.

Clouds

Salesforce has several different solutions that are in use by grantmaking organizations. Each of these solutions – or “Clouds” – has a different data model.

- [foundationConnect](#): A previous solution to manage grantmaking activities that has been retired by Salesforce and is no longer actively sold or developed.
- [Nonprofit Cloud](#): The current base Cloud for grantmaking activities.
- [Nonprofit Cloud for Grantmaking](#): The “Grantmaking” add-on can be combined with any other Salesforce Cloud. This is the most common combination in the philanthropic sector.
- [Nonprofit Success Pack and Managed Packages](#): A combination of packages aimed at solving common use cases for nonprofits, built on the Nonprofit Cloud.
- [Sales Cloud](#): In some cases where more customizable behavior or data objects are desired, grantmaking organizations may use the Sales Cloud.

Related Products

Salesforce offers additional products that can be integrated with their core platform and Clouds. Some of these products may impact the data available in the platform.

- **Agentforce:** Salesforce’s agentic AI platform that supports the creation of AI agents to perform autonomous tasks, which may include reading data from external sources.
- **Data 360 (formerly Data Cloud):** Allows organizations to connect data sources to Salesforce for data mapping, governance, and use by Agentforce.
- **Heroku:** Supports the development of custom applications that use Salesforce data and can be exposed as API services within Salesforce.

Additionally, there are third-party grantmaking products, such as [Amp Impact by Vera Solutions](#) and [GrantSmith by Deloitte](#), that are built on the Salesforce platform and may introduce their own data models and customizations.

Objects and Data Models

Across the philanthropic sector, there is broad variation in the use of Salesforce data objects and their associated data models. As noted above, each Cloud uses a different data model, and foundations may additionally opt to customize these base models to meet their local needs.

Salesforce maintains a [Data Model Gallery](#), which provides high-level information about database objects, fields and relationships. Information about the objects and fields present in a specific Salesforce implementation is available from the [Salesforce Metadata API](#), as well as in visualization tools like Schema Builder.

Organizations which use the Sales Cloud often create highly customized objects, which are not documented in the Data Model Gallery. Information about these objects and their associated fields would need to be provided by the implementing organization.

Document Management

Documents may be stored in Salesforce and can be exported by using the Salesforce sObject Blob Get API endpoint. The native features that support document management and are relevant for grantmaking include:

- **Files:** supports user upload of documents that can then be shared with team members. The uploaded files can be viewed and customized from all end devices.
- **Attachments:** supports attaching files of various types to data records.

Documents can also be stored in external systems. These documents are not directly exportable via Salesforce APIs and exporting them would likely require connecting directly to the system in which they are stored, including accounting for related security policies and configurations. There are third-party integrations that support additional features such as electronic signatures or collaborative editing of documents. These include:

- Generic productivity solutions such as SharePoint, Google Drive, Box, or DocuSign CLM. These can be connected to Salesforce via the [Salesforce Files Connect](#) function or third-party tools available in Salesforce AppExchange.
- Storage solutions such as Amazon S3 or Azure that are connected to Salesforce via third-party tools available in Salesforce AppExchange.
- Document management systems that are connected to Salesforce via a third-party app available in Salesforce AppExchange.

For all storage locations, it may be necessary to retrieve document metadata in addition to the files themselves to know which document types and versions should be exported as part of an archival package.

Existing Export Options

Salesforce currently provides several built-in mechanisms for exporting data: a backup tool, a desktop data loader, a reporting interface, and API access. Each offers different trade-offs in terms of filtering capability, attachment export support, and ease of use. For use cases that require more flexibility, like targeting specific grants, scheduling recurring exports, or exporting attachments alongside structured data, there are also third-party tools available that extend or replace Salesforce's capabilities (Table 1). The data available for export is governed by Salesforce access security tied to user identities.

Export tool	Filtering	Scheduling	Interface	Output Format	Export Attachments
Salesforce Backup Data Export	Object level only	Configurable only weekly or monthly	GUI	CSV	Supported
Salesforce Data Loader	Field level	Manual in GUI or automated via CLI	GUI or CLI with SOQL (Windows only)	CSV	Not supported
Salesforce Reports	Field level	Email attachments configurable to daily, weekly, or monthly	GUI	CSV	Not supported
Salesforce Own	Object level	Daily or on-demand	GUI	CSV	Supported
Salesforce Bulk API	Field level	Custom	Custom	CSV or JSON	Supported
Dataloader.io	Field level	Configurable to hourly, daily, weekly, or monthly	GUI or raw SOQL	CSV	Supported
Skyvia	Field level	Configurable to daily, weekly, or monthly	GUI or raw SQL	CSV	Supported

Table 1. Summary of primary export features for selected tools most relevant to archival export.

Existing Salesforce Functionality

Backup Data Export

Reference sources: [Data Export FAQs](#), [Trailhead Export Data learning unit](#)

[Backup data export](#) is Salesforce's built-in backup tool that is operated through the Salesforce web interface and can generate an export either on demand or automatically at a set frequency. Filtering is limited to selecting which objects to include; it does not support filtering specific records based on field values. Data is delivered as CSV files bundled in a ZIP, and attached binaries are included in the export.

Limitations of the backup data export include:

- Export filters cannot filter at the field level, so all fields are included in the export
- There are limits to how frequently exports can be triggered. Weekly exports are available in Enterprise, Performance, and Unlimited Editions. Monthly exports are available in all editions.
- No functionality to be able to target specific grants.
- If the total size of exported data is greater than 512 MB, the export generates multiple .zip files.
- The data export is not optimized for speed and may take a long time to complete.
- Only one file download is allowed at a time, and there is a 60-second wait required between downloads.

Data Loader

[Data Loader](#) is a client application that must be installed locally and is designed primarily for updating or [exporting data](#). It can be operated either from the user interface or a command-line interface for automated batch operations. Filtering is field level, configured via a query builder that generates Salesforce Object Query Language (SOQL), or written as raw SOQL. The data loader allows targeting specific objects and fields for export and supports field mapping. Data is delivered as CSV files with no attachments.

Requirements and limitations of the data loader include:

- No support for exporting attachments. Salesforce suggests using the weekly export feature in the online application to export attachments.
- The command line interface is only available in Windows.

Reports

[Reports](#) are Salesforce's built-in reporting tool, designed to give access to Salesforce data for analysis, viewing, and sharing. Reports are configured and run through Salesforce's custom reporting user interface and can be scheduled as a subscription to run automatically on a daily, weekly, or monthly basis [via email notifications and attachments](#). Reports are built around specific

objects, and filtering is field-level, supporting a range of operators and date or time-based values. Data is delivered as CSV files with no attachments.

[Limitations of the Reports functionality](#) include:

- No support to export attachments; reports only exports field data.
- Size limitations depending on report type and export format: tabular and summary reports are limited to 100,000 rows and 100 columns.
- The first 999 characters in a standard rich text area or a long text area are displayed in a report. For custom fields, only the first 254 characters are displayed.

Salesforce Own (formerly OwnBackup)

[Salesforce Own](#) incorporated the third-party OwnBackup, which was acquired by Salesforce in 2024. It supports automated backups, recovery, secure “archiving” and data seeding to protect and restore data. The focus of Salesforce Own is on backup and recovery within Salesforce, not data export out of Salesforce.

Salesforce APIs

[Salesforce APIs](#), particularly the [Bulk API](#), can extract both structured and unstructured data and integrate into existing data infrastructure. This provides a level of flexibility and automation possibilities but requires custom development resources to implement and manage. While the Bulk API is most practical for archival export, the Metadata API can also be used to understand the data schema. API calls are limited per organization, and access varies by Salesforce edition.

Third-party Solutions

A number of third-party tools exist to supplement or replace Salesforce's built-in export capabilities. All tools have an associated cost.

Backup

CloudAlly Salesforce Backup

[CloudAlly Salesforce Backup](#) provides automated backup, granular restore, sandbox seeding, and retention for Salesforce data. It exports data as CSV and is compatible with Data Loader. This tool is geared toward cybersecurity use cases for data protection and recovery.

Gearset

[Gearset](#) is a DevOps and backup solution designed for Salesforce. It provides automated backup and restore functionality, covering both metadata and data. It performs daily backups of standard and custom objects, storing them in cloud storage. The platform allows users to compare data between the live environment and historical backups, search for specific records, and export data to CSV. The tool is geared towards use cases for full backup and data recovery.

Spanning

[Spanning](#) (from Kaseya) is a backup and recovery solution designed for Salesforce. It provides manual or daily automated backups of data and metadata, granular search and restore, and sandbox seeding. Like other backup tools, it is primarily focused on data protection and disaster recovery with an emphasis on restoring data back to Salesforce, not export.

Extract, Transform, Load (ETL)

Dataloader.io

[Dataloader.io](#) is a web-based tool for importing and [exporting Salesforce data](#). It is operated through a web browser with no local installation required, and exports can be scheduled to run automatically on an hourly, daily, weekly, or monthly basis. Filtering is field level, configured through a visual query builder or written as raw SOQL. The tool targets specific objects and fields. Data is delivered as CSV files bundled in a ZIP, and [attached binaries can be included in the export](#). Exports use the Salesforce Bulk API or Batch API.

Skyvia

[Skyvia](#) is a cloud data platform that supports data integration and includes a [data export operation](#) for exporting cloud application or relational database data. It is operated through a web browser with no local installation required, and exports can be scheduled to run automatically on a daily, weekly, or monthly basis. Filtering is field level, configured through a visual query builder or written as raw SQL. The tool targets specific objects and fields. Multiple objects can be exported in a single operation. Data is delivered as CSV files bundled in a ZIP, and [attached binaries can be included in the export](#).

Conemis

[Conemis](#) is a migration automation tool focused on consolidating Salesforce instances or replacing/extending other CRM systems with Salesforce. It also includes [data extraction capabilities](#) that are geared more toward migration efforts than recurring exports and pulls raw source data and metadata from a connected application using Salesforce's SOAP or Bulk API. It is operated through a text-based [extract definition](#) editor with no visual query interface. Filtering is field-level. The tool targets specific objects and fields. Data can either be loaded directly to a destination system or downloaded and stored locally. Data delivery formats and attachment export support are not confirmed by available documentation.

Integration Platforms and Connectors

There are a number of platforms (iPaaS) and tools that can support integration pipelines to into other data platforms like Azure, Amazon Web Services, or Google Cloud Platform. These include products like [Informatica](#), [MuleSoft](#), and [Qlik Talend](#). While not export tools themselves, they can serve as a foundation to build an export solution using an interface like the Salesforce Bulk API. These products come at a significant cost but can facilitate export primarily in contexts where this infrastructure has already been implemented for other use cases.

Gap Analysis of Existing Solutions Against Archival Export Requirements

In the analysis below, the gaps between existing tools and export requirements are divided into three domains informed by what we know about archival export stakeholders and their motivations: data integrity and structure preservation; privacy, risk, and data governance; and operational accessibility and maintenance capacity. As summarized in Table 2 below, this analysis indicates that none of the available export options fully meet the requirements of archival export.

Privacy, Risk, and Data Governance

Relevant Requirements

- Allow users to select which database-backed fields should be included in an export so that fields containing PII or other sensitive information can be excluded.
- Allow users to specify which grant records should be exported based on data in a database-backed field, such as grant status or grant close date, ensuring that only grant information that is no longer actively in use is exported.

Gaps

- **High effort required to exclude sensitive information:** Many tools allow field-level filtering to remove sensitive data, but careful analysis and configuration of existing data is required to determine which fields to target. Given the variation of Salesforce Clouds and implementations, this is complex, burdensome, and cannot be generalized across different instances.
- **Limited options to remove sensitive data *and* export attachments.** The only native Salesforce tools that will export attached documents (Salesforce Backup and Salesforce Own) do not allow field-level filtering to remove PII or other sensitive data.

Operational Accessibility and Maintenance Capacity

Relevant Requirements

- Support grantmaking organizations of all sizes
- Export data on a pre-defined regular schedule or on demand

Gaps

- **Small organizations with limited funding and IT support lack options:** Built-in Salesforce tools like Reports and Data Loader meet many requirements for archival export, but do not export attachments. Cost is prohibitive for many third-party solutions. Where there are free tiers, there are also rate and feature limits that necessitate slower or more manual tasks.

API-based solutions require experience using Salesforce APIs including troubleshooting, navigating security issues, query construction, and an understanding of the data model and schema changes over time. These all present significant technical barriers for organizations with limited resources.

- Large organizations lack options to handle complex infrastructure without a considerable maintenance load and strategic coordination: Using APIs and/or third-party integrations for custom solutions is an ongoing maintenance load for IT Managers, contradicting the goal of transitioning to low-maintenance SaaS models. There is no turn-key product that wraps the API to enable archival export, especially given the variability of Salesforce implementations. Custom approaches also require ongoing strategic coordination between IT staff and information and knowledge managers to understand complex data architecture across systems over time, target only the required data and documents, administer integrations, and navigate security requirements.
- **On-demand and regular exports require significant resources to execute:** Frequent unscheduled exports with different requirements necessitate constructing multiple unique queries or reports and associated data post-processing that are time intensive. Scheduled regular exports require administrative and monitoring resources related to security, cost, schema changes over time, and the maintenance of any integrations with external tools.

Archival Export Requirement	Salesforce Reports	Salesforce Data Loader	Salesforce Backup Data Exporter	Backup and Recovery (Salesforce Own, CloudAlly, Gearset, Spanning)	Third-Party ETL (DataLoader.io, Syvia)	Salesforce APIs
Export database fields + attachments in original format	No attachments	No attachments	Includes both	Includes both	Includes both	Possible (must decode base64)
Export data to a single file, serialized as structured data	Multiple CSVs	Multiple CSVs	Multiple CSVs	Proprietary format/Multiple CSVs	Multiple CSVs	Yes, CSV or JSON (Bulk API v1 only for JSON)
Field-level selection (for sensitive data)	Manual per report	Manual per query	No (object-level only)	No (full backup)	Manual per query	Yes
Filter objects by data field (grant status/date)	Yes (report filters)	Yes (SOQL queries)	No	Some support (but designed for full backup)	Yes (Visual query, SQL, SOQL)	Yes (SOQL query)
Scheduled or on-demand exports	Yes, both	On-demand (requires script for schedule)	Scheduled only	Yes, both	Yes, both	On-demand (requires script/tool for schedule)
Support grantmaking orgs of all sizes	Yes, low-barrier	No, technical barriers	Yes, low-barrier	No, cost barriers	Possible, cost-barriers at scale	No, technical barriers

Table 2. Summary matrix of salesforce archival export solutions against defined requirements.

Conclusion

Because of the complexity of the platform, the range of institutional contexts, and the diversity of implementations in those institutions, there is no single path for archival export from Salesforce, and no existing export mechanism that produces archives-ready packages without additional processing or transformation actions. There are, however, a range of options that depend on local requirements, infrastructure, and capacity.

1. For organizations with the necessary development, integration, and data engineering capacity, the Salesforce Bulk and Metadata APIs provide the best foundation for archival export.
2. For organizations working at smaller volumes, the built-in Salesforce export tools are a good option, although a complete solution for archival export will likely require using a combination of multiple tools. This includes possibly supplementing workflows with simple third-party export tools like Dataloader.io, and handling post-processing of CSV outputs.
3. While none of the third-party tools we analyzed currently support all archival export requirements, organizations that already implement one of these tools may be able to customize or enhance it appropriately.

Consider Local Requirements and Regulations

While this report lays out generalized requirements for archival exports, grant-making organizations will have additional local requirements. Organizations should carefully consider the potential users and use of their exported data, identify the kinds of questions they hope to answer with the exported data and, conversely, what kinds of information they do not want to expose. They should also be aware of regulations governing user data which may impact these decisions.

Assess and Build on Current Infrastructure and Capacity

In addition to identifying local requirements, organizations implementing archival export from Salesforce should assess their current infrastructure to determine the feasibility of building on what is already implemented. For example, organizations that already support Salesforce data export to systems like enterprise data lakes or warehouses, reporting environments, or backup platforms should prioritize enhancing existing workflows and tools to accommodate the requirements of archival export, which will reduce implementation costs and long-term maintenance burdens.

Organizations should also carefully measure the expertise available to support archival export from Salesforce. For all the approaches identified above, a strong understanding of how the grantmaking process is reflected in Salesforce is essential. For approaches that require custom development, technical knowledge of Salesforce APIs and prior experience developing integrations for the platform is required. This capacity is needed over the long term, since any expertise necessary to

implement a solution (for example, knowledge of Salesforce's APIs) will also be needed to maintain that solution over time.

Implement Regular Exports

Organizations will also need to consider the timing of archival export. In general, a regularly scheduled export is recommended, rather than one tied to systems migration or events like anniversaries or leadership changes. Similarly, although limited-life foundations may consider deferring archival export until spend-down, this approach runs the risk of losing organizational knowledge about information in Salesforce.

Acknowledgements

Many thanks to Kelly Hardebeck and Lauren van Heerden from Conemis; Pierre Kaluzny from Sputnik Moment; Sally Vermaaten from the Gates Archive; Amy Gipson and Stefanie Terasaki from the Gates Foundation; and Myka Carroll, Marilyn Law, Sofie Gekhel, and Amy Mohler from Open Society Foundations for initial conversations that shaped the composition of the Advisory Committee as well as the overall direction of this initiative.